

Manuscript Details

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Title	Welfare impacts of climate-smart agriculture in Ghana. Does row planting and drought-tolerant maize varieties matter?
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Abstract

This study provides new evidence of the impact of climate-smart agriculture (CSA) – row planting and drought-tolerant maize varieties - on farm and welfare outcomes by estimating a multinomial endogenous switching regression model that corrects for selection bias and farmer heterogeneity in CSA choice. Application of our model to panel observations of 438 households in Ghana show that adoption of CSA increases both yield and intensity of maize commercialization but negatively affect own consumption. Specifically, the magnitude of the impact is relatively higher for adopters of row planting relative to adopters of drought-tolerant maize seeds. These results suggest the need for development practitioners to increase awareness and emphasize the importance of row planting as a key component of climate-smart agriculture.

Keywords Climate-smart agriculture; Multinomial endogenous switching regression; Farm and welfare impact; Ghana

Manuscript region of origin Africa

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Data will be made available on request

5th February, 2020

Editor-In-Chief
Land Use Policy

Dear Sir,

Please find attached the revised manuscript titled “**Welfare impacts of climate-smart agriculture in Ghana. Does row planting and drought-tolerant maize varieties matter?**” based on the reviewer’s comments received for further review and possible publication in your highly esteemed journal.

We strongly agree that by addressing the valuable and critical comments, our manuscript has improved significantly.

We thank the anonymous reviewers for the insightful comments to our manuscripts. We are also very thankful to you for giving us the opportunity to revise our manuscript. The manuscript is co-authored with Prince Maxwell Etwire, Tahirou Abdoulaye. The manuscript is neither published nor under consideration for publication elsewhere.

We strongly believe that this paper would provide further insight into our understanding of the welfare impact of climate-smart agriculture in developing and emerging economies.

Thank you very much

Sincerely yours,

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REVIEWER #1

No	Reviewers Comment	Author(s) Response
	Under introduction, paragraph two, second line and the subsequent statements under the paragraph need citations to support the programmes on soil health projects, conservation agriculture among others.	Thank you very much. All relevant citations are provided and highlighted red in the text.
	In page two, the argument about the challenges of cross-sectional data to panel data is not enough. Authors should provide enough justification for the relevance of panel data to cross-sectional data regarding their study too.	Thank you very much. We have provided the justifications for using panel data (Highlighted in red).
	In page three, the link between the preceding statement and the subsequent statement is not strong. Authors should rephrase their statements.	Thank you very much. The link has been strengthened and highlighted in red.
	In page four, under the last paragraph, authors should provide citations to support the emphatic statements such as increase in market participation and own consumption is likely to reduce household food diversification.	Thank you very much. The citation is provided and highlighted red in the text.
	In page, 14, the statement ‘labour constraints may be accounting for the decrease in the use of row planting is incomplete. Authors should check.	Thank you very much. Corrected and highlighted red in the text
	Page 15, the first line, authors should provide the reason for higher sales intensity in 2018 among non-adopters.	Thank you very much. We have provided the reason in the last sentence of the paragraph. We are careful with speculation given that other factors have not been controlled for, thus unable to make a conclusive statement.
	Under results and discussions, authors should check the interpretation of the female-headed household. It should read as ‘ <i>a male-headed household is 5% less likely to adopt improved maize varieties compared to female-headed household.</i> ’	Thank you very much. The interpretation we provided is correct. If male-headed household is 5% less likely to adopt improved maize variety then the alternative interpretation holds. Female headed households are 5% more likely to adopt.....compared to the male-headed households.
	Similarly, in the same page, authors should give convincing reasons why educated farmers are less likely to adopt improved varieties.	Thank you very much. Reason provided and highlighted in red.
	Page 19, authors should give reasons with citations if possible the reasons why fertiliser use is negatively associated with adoption of DTM varieties only. I am inclined to think that, considering the socioeconomic dynamics of the area, cost might be one of the reasons if not the major for the results. This is mainly because most improved varieties comes with associated	Thank you very much. We have provided reason(s) to buttress our findings. Highlighted red in text.

	cost of purchasing fertilisers in order to get optimum yield.	
	In page 20, Table 4, authors should give a footnote explaining the figures in parenthesis. It seems, the figures in parenthesis for sales intensity and own consumption are the p values but the maize yield is different. Authors should clarify that.	Thank you very much. The values in parentheses are standard errors. We have included it in the table note and highlighted red.
	In page 21, paragraph two, line 2, authors should rephrase the statement for better clarity and understanding. Also, in line three, under the same paragraph, further explanation is needed for clarity.	Thank you very much. The corrections have been effected and highlighted in red.
	Authors should check some of the references, as some of them do not have issue numbers. Eg. Abdoulaye and Awotide, 2018, Fentie and Beyene 2019 etc.	Thank you very much. Some of the papers do not have issue numbers upon further checking. However, we have provided the issue numbers for the existing ones.

REVIEWER #2

No	Reviewers Comment	Author(s) Response
1	It is advisable to frame the topic.	Thank you very much. The topic has been changed to “Welfare impacts of climate-smart agriculture in Ghana. Does row planting and drought-tolerant maize varieties matter?”
2	Better organize the methodology which in some parts is unclear.	Thank you very much. The methodology combines both theoretical and the empirical strategy in addressing the research questions. We begin by setting up the theoretical framework, stating the model and the problem associated with the model (consequences) thus the need for a more robust estimation technique. This led to the introduction of the multinomial endogenous switching regression model where we described the first and second stages and finally conclude with estimation of the average treatment effect on the treated.
3	The formulas must be explained with empirical consequences.	Thank you very much. All the formulas are well explained and references provided for further reading in the interest of brevity.
4	Add empirical fallout taking into account the interaction of the product's demand and supply.	Thank you very much. We recognize that interactions of maize demand and supply can influence our empirical results so we present our theoretical and empirical strategies (Section 2) as well as our empirical results (Section 4.2) under the assumption that “market conditions are favorable to smallholder farmers”. We have now cited Barrett (2008) to support our submission.
5	Review the abstract and english.	Thank you very much. Abstract modified and language improved.

Highlights

- ❖ The study evaluates the effect of row planting and drought tolerant maize variety on welfare outcomes in Ghana.
- ❖ Drought-tolerant maize variety increases yield 122kg/hectare and sales intensity by 0.09.
- ❖ Row planting increases yield and sales intensity by 271kg/hectare and 0.13 respectively but decreases own consumption by -0.11.
- ❖ The study highlights the effectiveness of row planting as a mechanism for increasing resilience in farming systems.
- ❖ The welfare effect can be sustained through awareness creation and emphasis on row planting.

Welfare impacts of climate-smart agriculture in Ghana. Does row planting and drought-tolerant maize varieties matter?

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1 **1. Introduction**

2 In Africa, 70% of the population are smallholder farmers who cultivate an average plot size of less
3 than 2 hectares (Alliance for a Green Revolution in Africa, AGRA, 2017). These farmers
4 especially those in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) rely on poor and unsustainable farming practices
5 leading to poor soil fertility (Grabowski et al., 2016) with subsequent decline in crop yield, and
6 high incidence of food insecurity and poverty (Kassie et al., 2015; Fisher et al., 2015). According
7 to Hansen et al. (2018), the livelihoods of agricultural households are mostly affected by these
8 constraints since they operate in environments characterised by high risks and weak institutions.
9 However, the agricultural sector is expected to lead the African transformation process given that
10 the sector has considerable untapped irrigation, vast uncultivated land for agricultural production,
11 and a huge potential to address the increasing demand for food and nutrition security due to
12 population growth, and issues relating to poverty (Fuglie, 2018; AGRA, 2017).

13

14 Despite the large share of Africans involved in agriculture and the potential of becoming food self-
15 sufficient, the region is inundated with high import bill which stands at US\$35 billion, and is
16 estimated to rise to US\$110 billion by 2025 (Adesina, 2017). To close this gap and achieve the
17 sustainable development goal 2 which seeks to end hunger, achieve food security and improved
18 nutrition and promote sustainable agriculture; development partners and African governments
19 have implemented projects and programs such as soil health projects, conservation agriculture,
20 agricultural value chain mentorship program, fertilizer subsidy programs among others (Brüntrup,
21 2011). These projects and programs are aimed at increasing land and labour productivity to achieve
22 sustainable food production. In Ghana, the government of Ghana has launched the “planting for
23 food and jobs program” as a strategy to build the capacity of farmers and increase their access to

24 quality certified seeds and fertilizers through a private sector led marketing framework. The
25 program also seeks to build the capacity of extension agents and adequately resource them to train
26 farmers on good agronomic practices and commercialization of outputs over an e-agriculture
27 platform (Ministry of Food and Agriculture, 2017). Improved maize variety is one of the target
28 crops for the program since it is widely cultivated by household for both consumption and
29 commercialization. In view of this, any complementary support to the maize sub-sector will have
30 a wide ripple effect on incomes and food security.

31

32 To increase yield and sustain household income in the midst of climate change and other related
33 risks, development practitioners argue for the adoption of climate-smart agriculture (CSA). For
34 example, drought-tolerant maize (DTM) seed is being promoted among resource-poor farmers to
35 lower the risks of crop failure resulting from among others, low and uneven rainfall pattern in
36 different agro-ecological zones (Fisher et al., 2015). Row planting, a component of climate smart
37 agricultural (CSA) also has the potential of increasing agricultural productivity and incomes as
38 well as building resilience against climate shocks (Fantie and Beyene, 2019; Teklewold et al.,
39 2017).

40

41 Several studies have evaluated the impact of single agricultural technology use on welfare of farm
42 households (Zang et al., 2017; Abdulai, 2016; Asfaw et al., 2016; Jaleta et al., 2016; Khonje et al.,
43 2015; Bezu et al., 2014). Issahaku and Abdulai (2019) find that adoption of climate smart practices
44 positively and significantly impacts on food and nutrition security. Abdulai and Huffman (2014)
45 establish that adoption of soil and water conservation measures impact positively on yields and net
46 farm revenues. Some studies (Ng'ombe et al., 2017; Teklewold and Mekonnen, 2017; Manda et

47 al., 2016) have used cross-sectional data to analyse the economic impact of multiple technology
48 adoption. Such results are very insightful but unable to deal with econometric issues (unobserved
49 heterogeneity due to time-varying characteristics) associated with the use of cross-section data
50 (Michler et al., 2019). However, panel data is able to produce a more accurate inference of model
51 parameters, accounts for dynamism in adoption (uncovering dynamic relationships), and overcome
52 measurement errors that may bias parameter estimates (Hsiao, 2007). Using panel data, Khonje et
53 al. (2018) find that adopting improved seed and conservation agricultural practices impact
54 positively on maize yield and income but negatively on poverty. Despite the numerous studies on
55 the economic and welfare impact of improved maize varieties in SSA, there is limited evidence on
56 the welfare impact of row planting as a complement to improved seed. A more recent study that
57 uses cross-sectional data show that row planting impacts positively on per capita consumption and
58 crop income per hectare (Fentie and Beyene, 2019). However, their study is limited in terms of
59 identifying how other technologies complement row planting.

60

61 This study contributes to the literature by identifying the relevant factors influencing the adoption
62 of row planting and improved seed. Secondly, the study adds to the literature on agricultural
63 innovation systems by using a panel data and Multinomial Endogenous Switching Regression
64 (MESR) model to establish how row planting and DTM variety impacts on yield, intensity of
65 maize commercialization and own consumption per adult equivalent unit (AEU). Finally, the study
66 demonstrates the effectiveness of row planting as a mechanism for increasing resilience in farming
67 systems.

68

69 The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the theoretical and empirical
70 strategy employed by the study while section 3 discusses and describes the data. Section 4 presents
71 the empirical results and discussion with section 5 highlighting the main conclusions and
72 implications of the study.

73

74 **2. Theoretical Framework and Empirical Strategy**

75 The decision to use **CSA** practice is a behavioural response thus modelled within the random utility
76 framework (Kassie et al., 2018; Ali and Abdulai, 2010) where a farmer chooses a component of
77 the **CSA** practices that increase utility. Following the argument of Panenell et al. (2014), we
78 consider a household's decision to adopt **CSA** practices in a reference year a constrained
79 optimization problem where the polychotomous adoption decision depends on a number of factors
80 including available information, relative costs and benefits of **CSA**, and socioeconomic conditions.
81 A household may decide to adopt a single or a combination of the **CSA** practices such as DTM
82 variety (IMP), row planting (ROW), and a combination of row planting and DTM variety
83 (IMPROW).

84

85 Given that farmers make production decisions regarding the optimum input choice, those decisions
86 can be modelled based on expected profit. A farmer will select any of the choice sets (of **CSA**
87 practices) if the expected profit from adoption is higher than the expected profit from non-adoption
88 as follows:

$$89 \quad \pi_{it}^{*CSA} = p_{it}Q_{it}^{*CSA} - \sum_{j=1}^J \omega_{jit}Z_{jit}^{*CSA} > \pi_{it}^{*NCSA} = p_{it}Q_{it}^{*NCSA} - \sum_{j=1}^J \omega_{jit}Z_{jit}^{*NCSA} \quad (1)$$

90

91 where Q_{it}^{CSA} and Q_{it}^{NCSA} are the respective vector of outputs for **CSA** and **non-CSA (NCSA)**
92 farmers; p_{it} is a vector of output prices which is considered to be same for both category of farmers;
93 ω_{jit} and Z_{it} are vectors of input prices and inputs respectively.

94

95 We expect that the welfare pathway effect of CSA adoption will be realized through an increase
96 in crop yield. Adoption of **CSA** practice will lead to an increase in crop yield *ceteris paribus* which
97 will likely increase market participation (intensity of commercialization) assuming that market
98 conditions are favourable (**Barrett, 2008**). With increased market participation, own consumption
99 is likely to reduce due to increased sales. If the outcome variables are a linear function of the
100 adoption decision, along with a vector of other explanatory variables X , and regional dummy
101 variables D_v , then the following equation holds:

102

$$103 \quad Y_{jit} = \vartheta X_{jit} + \beta T_{jit} + D_v + c_i + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (2)$$

104 where Y_{it} is the outcome variable, T_{it} represents an indicator variable for **CSA** adoption, ϑ and β
105 are vectors of parameters to be estimated, c_i is unobserved time-constant factors, and ε_{it} is a mean
106 zero, identically and independently distributed (iid) random error assumed to be uncorrelated with
107 the explanatory variables. The parameter β accurately measures the impact of adoption on the
108 outcome variable under the condition that farmers are randomly assigned to treatment and non-
109 treatment groups (Faltermeier and Abdulai, 2009). Direct estimation of β will be biased given that
110 the adoption of **CSA** practices was non-random. Secondly, farmers may self-select and the
111 decisions to adopt are likely to be influenced by unobserved human (motivation, entrepreneurial
112 ability, preferences, innovative ability, etc.) and farm characteristics (average soil quality or
113 fertility) and observed factors that may be correlated with the outcome variables (Panenell et al.

114 2014; Marenya and Barrett, 2009). For example, risk averse farmers may be more likely to adopt
115 a single **CSA** practice while risk-lovers may be more likely to adopt combinations of **CSA**
116 practices. The differences in the level of adoption may have heterogeneous effect on the outcome.
117 In view of the above challenges, there is a need to address self-selection and unobserved
118 heterogeneity associated with economic evaluations of the non-random adoption of innovations
119 such as **CSA** practices.

120

121 To address the problem of selection bias, several studies (Martey et al., 2019; Khonje et al., 2015;
122 Kassie et al., 2011) used the propensity score matching (PSM) method. According to Jaleta et al.
123 (2016) and Abdulai (2016), PSM is unable to correct for selection bias attributable to unobserved
124 factors. The use of fixed effects (FE) model controls for the endogeneity problem (arising from
125 unobserved heterogeneity) by eliminating the effects of time-constant factors. Employing the FE
126 model on the adoption of **CSA** practices may be problematic based on the assumption that the
127 model difference out the correlation between the individual effects and the explanatory variables.
128 However, some studies have argued that this is a strict assumption since the economic outcome of
129 **CSA** can be heterogeneous as a result of both observed and unobserved characteristics (Kassie et
130 al. 2018, Suri, 2011). The FE model also assumes that unobserved time-constant variables are the
131 only omitted variables in estimating the use of **CSA** practices on the outcomes. Suri (2011) argues
132 that this assumption is less likely to hold given that households might move in and out of **CSA**
133 practices during the period of the panel as a result of changes in unobservable factors that may also
134 affect the outcomes.

135

136 We employ the multinomial endogenous switching regression (MESR)¹ to account for selection
137 bias and endogeneity arising from both observed and unobserved heterogeneity. Application of the
138 MESR have several advantages. First, it corrects for the selection bias by computing an inverse
139 Mills ratio (IMR) based on the theory of truncated normal distribution (Malikov and Kumbhakar,
140 2014; Bourguignon et al., 2007). Second, it enables the construction of counterfactuals based on
141 returns to the characteristics of CSA adopters and non-adopters (Kassie et al., 2017). Third, it
142 allows for an interaction between the CSA technology choice set and the explanatory variables to
143 capture the effect of CSA on a shift of both intercept and slope of the outcome equation (Adoulaye
144 et al., 2018; Kassie et al., 2017; Di Falcao and Veronesi, 2013). Finally, the model identifies the
145 specific choice of CSA practices with the highest outcome effect (Wu and Babcock, 1998).

146
147 The MESR is a two-stage simultaneous estimation technique. The first stage models farmers'
148 choice of CSA using a multinomial logit selection (MNLS) equation by accounting for unobserved
149 heterogeneity. The IMRs calculated from the first stage are included in the outcome equation as
150 additional covariates to account for selection bias from time-varying unobserved heterogeneity.
151 The outcome equation is estimated using Ordinary Least Squares (OLS).

152
153 *2.1 First stage: Multinomial logit selection model*
154 As earlier stated, the first stage estimation of the factors that influence the choice of CSA is modelled within
155 the random utility framework where a farmer i in time t chooses a CSA technology set ($j = 1, \dots, 3$)

¹ This is a specific class of panel endogenous switching regression model proposed as by Malikov and Kumbhakar (2014). The MESR is applicable in this case due to the polychotomous nature of the choice of CSAs.

156 that maximizes expected utility (U_{jit}). A farm household will choose a **CSA** technology set j if its
 157 expected utility is relatively higher than other technology set k i.e. $\rho_{1it} = \max_{k \neq j} (U_{kit}^* - U_{jit}^*) < 0$.

158 Assuming the utility from choosing a **CSA** technology set j can be represented by the latent
 159 variable U_{jit}^* . Following Khonje et al. (2018), we specify the latent model that describes farmers'
 160 **CSA** adoption behaviour as:

$$161 \quad U_{jit}^* = \delta_j X_{jit} + \varphi_j \bar{X}_{ji} + \varepsilon_{jit} \quad \text{where } \varepsilon_{jit} = c_i + \eta_{jit} \quad (3)$$

162 with

$$163 \quad U = \begin{cases} 1 \text{ if } U_{jit}^* > \max_{k \neq 1} (U_{kit}^*) \text{ or } \rho_{1it} < 0 \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ J \text{ if } U_{jit}^* > \max_{k \neq j} (U_{kit}^*) \text{ or } \rho_{jit} < 0 \end{cases} \quad \forall k \neq j \quad (4)$$

164 where X_{jit} is a vector of observed covariates (demographic, farm characteristics, wealth indicators,
 165 access to extension and regional dummies² that accounts for temporal and spatial differences in
 166 agro-ecology and institution) that affect the probability of choosing a **CSA** technology set; \bar{X}_{ji} is
 167 the mean of all time-varying covariates; δ and φ are vector of parameters to be estimated and c_i
 168 and η_{jit} represent the household specific heterogeneity and time-varying unobserved factors or
 169 idiosyncratic errors, respectively. A correlation between the unobserved factors and explanatory
 170 variables ($E[\eta_{jit}|X_{jit}] \neq 0$) could lead to inconsistent estimate of the MNLS model. Based on the
 171 assumption that η_{jit} is independent and identically Gumbel distributed across all **CSA** choice sets

² Please refer to Khonje et al. (2018) and Kassie et al. (2017) for more detailed explanation.

172 (i.e. the independence of irrelevant alternatives (IIA) hypothesis) (Bourguignon et al., 2007),
 173 equation (3) leads to a multinomial logit model (McFadden, 1973) where the probability (P_{jit}) that
 174 a farmer i at time t will choose technology j out of J options can be expressed as:

$$175 \quad P_{jit} = \Pr(\rho_{1it} < 0 \mid X_{jit}) = \frac{\exp(\delta_j X_{jit} + \varphi_j \bar{X}_{ji})}{\sum_{k \neq 1}^J \exp(\delta_k X_{kit} + \varphi_k \bar{X}_{ki})} \quad (5)$$

176 We estimate equation (5) using a pooled MNLS model with correction for unobserved
 177 heterogeneity using the Mundlak (1978) and Wooldridge (2010) approach where the time-
 178 invariant unobserved effect (c_i) is modeled as a linear projection of the means of all time-varying
 179 observed explanatory variables (\bar{X}_{ji}) as: $c_i = \pi \bar{X}_{ji} + \alpha_i$.

180

181 2.2 Second stage: Multinomial endogenous switching regression model (MESR)

182 The second stage estimates the impacts of **CSA** choice sets (IMP₀ROW₀—non-adopters as
 183 reference category; IMP₁ROW₀—adopters of DTM variety; IMP₀ROW₁—adopters of row
 184 planting only; IMP₁ROW₁—adopters of both improved varieties and row planting) on farm level
 185 and welfare outcomes. However, the IMP₁ROW₁ category of farmers were dropped due to less
 186 data points. The choice of a specific **CSA** technology leads to a separate outcome equations with
 187 the treatment effects (of interest) being a binary comparison of the actual and counterfactual
 188 outcomes for **CSA** adoption and non-adoption. Following Kassie et al. (2018) and Khonje et al
 189 (2018), the outcome equation for each possible regime j with selection bias correction term is
 190 specified as:

$$\begin{cases}
 \text{Regime 1: } Y_{1it} = \beta_1 M_{1it} + \sigma_1 \hat{\lambda}_{1it} + \vartheta_1 \bar{M}_{1i} + \mu_{1it} & \text{if } U = 1 \\
 \cdot \\
 \cdot \\
 \cdot \\
 \cdot \\
 \cdot \\
 \text{Regime } J: Y_{jit} = \beta_j M_{jit} + \sigma_j \hat{\lambda}_{jit} + \vartheta_j \bar{M}_{ji} + \mu_{jit} & \text{if } U = J
 \end{cases} \quad j = 2, 3 \quad (6)$$

192
 193 where Y_{jit} represents the outcome associated with the selected regime $j(j = 0, \dots, J)$ and observed
 194 for all possible combination of **CSA** practices used, M_{jit} represents a vector of explanatory
 195 variables, \bar{M}_{ji} represents the means of all time-varying variables included to control for unobserved
 196 heterogeneity (Mundlak, 1978; Wooldridge, 2010), σ is the covariance between ε_{jit} (first stage)
 197 and μ_{jit} (second stage), $\hat{\lambda}_{jit}$ ³ is the IMR calculated from the estimated probabilities in equation
 198 (5).

199
 200 The inclusion of the IMRs in equation (6) leads to a consistent estimate of β_j and ϑ_j using OLS.
 201 Given that the second stage outcome model include estimates from the first stage selection model,
 202 the standard errors in equation (6) are bootstrapped to account for heteroscedasticity (Khonje et
 203 al., 2018). Even though equation (6) can be identified using non-linearity of the selection model,
 204 it is important to observe exclusion restriction (Di Falcao, 2014), for. Following previous studies
 205 (Khonje et al., 2018; Zeng et al., 2017; Abdulai, 2016; Kassie et al., 2015), we exclude access to
 206 extension services (dummy and continuous) and extension contacts from our outcome equations.
 207 Agricultural extension agents are the main source of agricultural information regarding new

³ The IMR is computed as $\hat{\lambda}_{jit} = \sum_{k \neq j}^j \rho_j \left[\frac{\hat{p}_{ki} \ln(\hat{p}_{ki})}{1 - \hat{p}_{ki}} + \ln(\hat{p}_{jit}) \right]$ where ρ is the correlation between ε_{jit} and μ_{jit}

208 technologies and practices. The only means of causal impact is through adoption of **CSA** given
 209 that farmers will adopt modern technologies when they have adequate information about the
 210 benefits. The admissibility of the instrument is established through a simple falsification⁴ test
 211 proposed by Di Falcao et al. (2011). The results confirm that the excluded variables have
 212 significant effect on **CSA** practices but do not significantly influence the outcome variables of non-
 213 adopters (Table A1).

214

215

216 *2.3 Estimation of average treatment effects on the treated (ATT)*

217 The treatment effect on the treated due to the adoption of **CSA** is computed by comparing the
 218 expected values of outcomes of adopters and non-adopters of **CSA** in actual and counterfactual
 219 scenarios. The actual expected outcomes of adopters is expressed as:

$$220 \quad E(Y_{jit}|U = j, M_{jit}, \bar{M}_{ji}, \hat{\lambda}_{jit}) = \beta_j M_{jit} + \vartheta_j \bar{M}_{ji} + \sigma_j \hat{\lambda}_{jit} \quad (7a)$$

221 The expected outcomes of adopters had they decided not to adopt (counterfactual)

$$222 \quad E(Y_{1it}|U = j, M_{jit}, \bar{M}_{ji}, \hat{\lambda}_{jit}) = \beta_1 M_{jit} + \vartheta_1 \bar{M}_{ji} + \sigma_1 \hat{\lambda}_{jit} \quad (7b)$$

223 Equation (7b) represents the outcome for what **CSA** adopters would have obtained if the
 224 coefficients on their characteristics ($M_{jit}, \bar{M}_{ji}, \hat{\lambda}_{jit}$) were the same as the coefficients on the
 225 characteristics of non-adopters (Khonje et al., 2018; Kassie et al., 2017; Teklewold et al., 2013).

⁴ A falsification test certifies the admissibility of the selection instrument as a valid instrument: if a variable is an appropriate selection instrument, it will only influence the adoption decision, but not the welfare outcomes.

226 The ATT⁵ is computed as the difference between equation (7a) and equation (7b) (Khonje et al.,
227 2018; Kassie et al., 2017) as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} 228 \quad ATT &= E(Y_{jit}|U = j, M_{jit}, \bar{M}_{ji}, \hat{\lambda}_{jit}) - E(Y_{1it}|U = j, M_{jit}, \bar{M}_{ji}, \hat{\lambda}_{jit}) \\ 229 \quad &= M_{jit}(\beta_j - \beta_1) + \hat{\lambda}_{jit}(\sigma_j - \sigma_1) + \bar{M}_{ji}(\vartheta_j - \vartheta_1) \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

230 The first term of equation (8) ($\beta_j - \beta_1$) captures the expected change in the mean outcome due to
231 the differences in coefficients of the observed characteristics. The second ($\sigma_j - \sigma_1$) and third
232 ($\vartheta_j - \vartheta_1$) terms in equation (8) corrects selection bias and endogeneity originating from
233 unobserved heterogeneity (Khonje et al., 2018).

234 Our indicators for farm level and welfare outcomes are yield (measured as the total output per
235 hectare), intensity of maize commercialization (measured as the ratio of quantity of maize sold to
236 the total output) and own consumption⁶ per AEU (measured as the quantity of maize available for
237 consumption divided by adult equivalent unit). The data is limited in terms of exploring other
238 important welfare indicators such as poverty and food security.

239

240 **3. Data and descriptive statistics**

241 The study was conducted in all the maize growing regions of Ghana except the Greater Accra
242 Region (Fig. 1). The study relied on a panel data (2013 and 2018) which was collected under a
243 joint collaboration between the Consultative Group of International Agricultural Research
244 (CGIAR) (i.e. International Food Policy and Research Institute (IFPRI) and International Institute
245 of Tropical Agriculture (IITA)) and two institutes of Ghana's Council for Scientific and Industrial

⁵ The ATT is computed based on the post-estimation prediction of the actual and counterfactual expected value of the outcomes for a household that adopts technology j after estimating the MESR in equation (6).

⁶ Own consumption is computed by subtracting the amount of maize sold, gifted and seed from the household's own production.

254 A multi-stage sampling techniques (clustered and randomized sampling procedure) was employed
255 in the selection of the farmers. The sampling framework was all maize-producing districts with
256 more than 3,000 hectares (average for 2009-2011) under maize cultivation. In the first stage, the
257 proportional⁷ probability sampling approach was used to assign more weight to districts with
258 higher maize productions and followed with random selection of 30 districts. In the second stage,
259 enumeration areas (EAs) were randomly selected in each sampled district. The definition of an EA
260 was based on the same classifications and boundaries as used in Ghana's Population and Housing
261 Census and the country's Living Standards Survey (GLSS) (Ragasa et al., 2013). A total of 90
262 EAs were randomly selected. The third stage was followed by random selection of seven farmers
263 in each of the sampled EAs. In summary, a total of 630 farmers were randomly sampled from 90
264 EAs in 30 districts of Ghana. Following the definition of Ragasa et al. (2013), a farmer in our
265 sample is defined as one who managed and took decisions about a maize plot during the major
266 season of 2012 (with a minimum of 0.5 acres, or 0.2 hectare, of maize area included in the list of
267 maize farmers). A follow up survey of the same households was conducted in 2019 to generate a
268 panel unit for the analysis. We interviewed 555 households (representing 88% of initial households
269 in 2013) during the endline survey using the same set of questionnaires administered in 2013. Out
270 of the 555 farmers, we observed an attrition effect of 20% bringing the total sampled units to 438.
271 The attrition effect was mainly due to migration, death, *inter alia*. To achieve a balanced household
272 panel, we dropped households who were not present at the time of the survey.

273

⁷ The proportional probability sampling technique assigns districts with a larger production area of maize a higher probability of being selected. The selected districts represent 40 percent of the total maize production area (and 39 percent of the total production in tons or 37 percent of total acreage) in Ghana between 2009 and 2011 (Ragasa et al., 2013).

274 The data contains information on household demography, farm characteristics, farm management
275 practices, soil improvement technologies, seed source, adoption of DTM varieties, information on
276 extension services related to crop production, risk preferences, and pattern of maize utilization. In
277 this study, we refer to **CSA** as adoption of DTM varieties and row planting. An adopter is
278 considered to be a farmer who have used the farm technologies for at least a year during the period
279 of the survey. DTM variety and row planting are defined as a dummy variable taking a value of 1
280 if a farm household uses the technologies. We generated a multinomial choice variable by
281 categorizing households according to their adoption of the two farm technologies in isolation.

282

283 Table 1 shows the outcome and explanatory variables (demography, farm, and institutional
284 characteristics of the farm households) used in the analysis. Table A2 in the appendix reports the
285 same outcome and explanatory variables based on adoption of **CSA**. The average yield, sales
286 intensity, and own consumption per AEU are 1152kg/ha, 0.69, and 0.64 respectively. By
287 disaggregating the farm and welfare outcomes based on year, we observed that yield and sales
288 intensity are relatively higher in 2013 than in 2018. However, for own consumption per AEU, the
289 value is higher in 2018. The proportion of farm households who adopted DTM variety increased
290 from 59% in 2013 to 82% in 2018 while the proportion of households who practice row planting
291 decreased from 75% in 2013 to 63% in 2018. **The high level of DTM variety adoption may be
292 attributed to the vigorous promotion and technical support provided to farmers by national and
293 international research organizations while high cost of labour may be accounting for the decrease
294 in the use of row planting.** Table A2 in the appendix shows that adopters of **CSA** (IMP_1ROW_0 ,
295 and IMP_0ROW_1) obtain higher maize yield and sales intensity than non-adopters (IMP_0ROW_0).

296

302 Conversely, non-adopters record a higher sales intensity in 2018 than adopters. With the exception
 303 of adopters of row planting, adopters of improved maize record higher own consumption per AEU
 304 in 2013 but the trend changes in 2018 where all the adopters recorded higher own consumption
 305 per AEU than the non-adopters (Table A2). **Given that the descriptive statistics are unconditional
 306 associations, we are unable to attribute the changes in farm and welfare outcomes to the adoption
 307 of CSA since other factors may be driving the changes.**

308 Table 1: Descriptive statistics by survey year

Variables	2013		2018		Pooled sample	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
<i>Outcome variables</i>						
Yield (kg/ha)	1199.10	1082.67	1104.28	1279.59	1152.52	1183.78
Sales intensity	0.74	0.26	0.64	0.31	0.69	0.29
Own consumption per AEU	0.59	0.81	0.69	0.89	0.64	0.85
<i>Treatment variables</i>						
Planted improved varieties (1=yes)	0.59	0.49	0.82	0.38	0.71	0.46
Practice row planting (1=yes)	0.75	0.43	0.63	0.48	0.69	0.46
<i>Explanatory variables</i>						
Gender of household head (1=male)	0.78	0.42	0.23	0.42	0.50	0.50
Age of household head (years)	44.49	11.72	49.21	11.26	46.80	11.73
Education of household head (years)	6.44	5.01	5.54	5.57	5.99	5.31
Nativity (1=native)	0.63	0.48	0.64	0.48	0.63	0.48
Household size (number)	8.52	5.46	8.40	6.31	8.46	5.90
Practice intercropping (1=yes)	0.39	0.49	0.09	0.29	0.25	0.43
Distance to plot (minutes)	43.59	36.64	46.97	40.02	45.25	38.36
Owns land (1=yes)	3.41	1.89	3.27	1.18	3.34	1.60
Farm size (hectare)	1.56	1.54	1.80	2.24	1.68	1.92
Slope (1=slope)	0.44	0.50	0.32	0.47	0.38	0.49
Model farmer (1=yes)	0.27	0.44	0.10	0.30	0.18	0.39
Use fertilizer (1=yes)	0.50	0.50	0.57	0.50	0.53	0.50
Fertilizer use (years)	3.30	3.69	6.67	4.24	4.52	4.21
Owns bicycle (1=yes)	0.52	0.50	0.94	0.23	0.73	0.44
Owns motor (1=yes)	0.19	0.40	0.95	0.23	0.57	0.50
Owns sprayer (1=yes)	0.65	0.48	0.93	0.25	0.79	0.41
<i>Instrumental variables</i>						
Distance to extension (kilometers)	11.61	29.52	12.94	56.82	12.27	45.19
Member of FBO (1=yes)	0.29	0.46	0.41	0.49	0.35	0.48
Household head contact extension (1=yes)	0.28	0.45	0.49	0.50	0.39	0.49
Extension contact household head (1=yes)	0.50	0.50	0.55	0.50	0.53	0.50

309 Notes: SD refers to standard deviations. Source: Authors computation based on IITA-IFPRI panel survey, 2018

310 The gender distribution across the sampled households is the same. Sampled households are
 311 relatively young, natives with 8 household members and 6 years of formal education. With respect

309 to farm characteristics, 25%, 18%, and 53% of the farmers practice intercropping, are model
 310 farmers, and use fertilizer, respectively. About 38% of the farmers cultivate maize on steep lands.
 311 The average farm size and walking distance to the nearest farm plot is 1.68 hectares and 45
 312 minutes, respectively. Farmers travel an average distance of 12 kilometers to the nearest extension
 313 office. About 35%, 39%, and 53% of farmers are members of FBOs, have contact with agricultural
 314 extension agents, and have been visited by extension agents, respectively.

315
 316 We further examined the transition and switching behaviour of farm households with respect to
 317 the use of CSA during the two periods (Table 2). The study identified four categories of CSA users
 318 – “Non-users” (farm household who never used any of the CSA in both periods); “Discontinued
 319 users” (farm household who uses a specific CSA in 2013 but not in 2018); “New-users” (farm
 320 household who did not use the specific CSA in 2013 but adopted in 2018); and “Stayers” (farm
 321 households that adopted the same CSA in both periods). The data indicate that 6% and 13% of the
 322 sample households are non-users of improved varieties and row planting, respectively and about
 323 45% and 36% of the sampled households switch in and out of improved varieties and row planting,
 324 respectively between 2013 and 2018. For stayers, the data shows that 49% and 51% used improved
 325 varieties and row planting in both periods. Household behaviour regarding dis-adoption and new
 326 adoption may be driven by differences in observed and unobserved time-constant and time-varying
 327 factors.

328
 329 Table 2: Transitions in CSA practices (%) over the sample periods (2013 and 2018)

Good Agricultural Practices	Non-users	Discontinued	New-users	Stayers
Improved varieties	6.39	11.19	33.79	48.63
Row planting	12.79	24.43	11.64	51.14

330

331

332 **4. Results and discussion**

333 *4.1 Determinants of adoption of CSA*

334 The marginal effects of the first stage (equation 5) MNL regression are presented in Table 3. The
335 results show that factors influencing the choice of CSA differ significantly across technology
336 choices. The Wald test suggests that the explanatory variables included in the MNL selection
337 model provide a good explanation regarding the choice of CSA. The Mundlak and instrumental
338 variables significantly explain the choice of CSA which suggests that failure to account for
339 unobserved heterogeneity and endogeneity will lead to a biased estimate of CSA choice on the
340 outcome variables. Based on the results, the use of pooled MNL selection model is appropriate.

341

342 Demographic characteristics such as gender and years of education significantly influence the
343 adoption of DTM variety (IMP_1ROW_0). Female-headed households are 5% more likely to adopt
344 improved varieties compared to male-headed households. Consistent with the findings of Khonje
345 et al. (2018) and Teklewold et al. (2013), educated farmers are more likely to adopt both DTM
346 varieties and row planting. Education is expected to increase farmers' receptivity and utilization
347 of modern technologies. However, the results indicate that education decreases the probability of
348 adopting only improved varieties. The results contradicts the findings of Bezu et al. (2014) who
349 find that education increases the probability and intensity of adopting improved maize varieties in
350 Malawi. **Educated household heads are likely to engage in off-farm activities that guarantees**
351 **relatively high and reliable income thus reducing their effort in agricultural activities.** In Ghana
352 (especially the northern part—Upper East, Upper West and Northern regions), most of the DTM
353 seeds were distributed to farmers through a development project, and therefore, farmers are in
354 these regions are less likely to buy improved seed. Household size increases the adoption of row

355 planting (IMP_0ROW_1) but decreases the adoption of DTM varieties. Row planting is labour-
 356 intensive thus the positive correlation with household size. The results is consistent with Fentie
 357 and Beyene (2019) who find a positive relationship between household size and row planting in
 358 Ethiopia. Nativity (form of social capital) increases the probability of using improved maize seed.
 359 Natives usually have access to communal resource such as land for agricultural activities and more
 360 likely to benefit from agricultural development programs.

361

362 Table 3: Marginal effect of adoption of agricultural technologies

Variables	(IMP ₁ ROW ₀)		(IMP ₀ ROW ₁)	
	Marginal effect	Robust Std. error	Marginal effect	Robust Std. error
Gender (1=male)	-0.053*	0.028	-0.032	0.029
Age (log)	0.052	0.122	0.020	0.132
Years of education (log)	-0.030**	0.012	-0.009	0.012
Household size (log)	-0.070*	0.039	0.094*	0.049
Distance to farm plot (log)	-0.014	0.018	-0.038*	0.019
Fertilizer use (years)	-0.105***	0.025	-0.019	0.024
Plot size (log)	0.044	0.044	0.006	0.047
Land ownership (1=yes)	-0.001	0.013	0.020	0.015
Nativity (1=ative)	0.048*	0.028	-0.028	0.028
Slope of farmland (1=slope)	-0.017	0.054	0.098*	0.056
Model farmer (1=yes)	-0.061	0.040	-0.050	0.035
Practice intercropping (1=yes)	0.034	0.054	0.062	0.060
Owens motor (1=yes)	0.110**	0.045	-0.227***	0.048
Extension contact farmer	-0.003	0.045	0.083***	0.050
Farmer contact extension	-0.055	0.050	-0.018	0.049
Distance to extension (log)	0.012	0.017	0.018	0.016
Mundlak variables	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Region FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Joint significance of instrumental variables χ^2 (3)	6.65*			
Joint significance of time-varying covariates: χ^2 (36)	69.41***			
Wald χ^2 (60)	157.14***			

363 Notes: The reference category is non-adoption (IMP_0ROW_0). IMP_1ROW_0 — only DTM variety; IMP_0ROW_1 — only
 364 row planting. The Mundlak device was incorporated in the estimation but the variables (mean of the time-varying
 365 explanatory variables) are not presented in the interest of brevity. Source: Authors estimation based on IITA-IFPRI
 366 panel survey, 2018.

367

368

369 Distance to farm plots decreases the adoption of row planting. Modern technologies are more likely

370 to be adopted on farm plots closer to the households. Fertilizer use is negatively associated with

371 the adoption of only DTM varieties. The finding could be due to the complementarity or
372 substitutability between fertilizer and CSA. In addition, cost of fertilizer may be driving the low
373 adoption of DTM seed given a farmer needs to apply fertilizer to DTM seed in order to get
374 optimum yield. There is the need to encourage farmers to complement DTM variety with fertilizer.
375 The results further show that adoption of row planting is positively related with slope of farm plot.
376 Ownership of motor bicycle increases the adoption of DTM (11%) but decreases the probability
377 of adopting only row planting (23%). Khonje et al. (2018) found a similar result where assets
378 increase the adoption of improved maize and conservation practices in Zambia. Farmers who own
379 assets can liquidate it when exposed to extreme negative weather and income shocks and invest in
380 modern inputs and CSA practices. The probability of only adopting row planting is higher for
381 farmers who have contact with agricultural extension agents. Consistent with our findings, Fentie
382 and Beyene (2019) find a positive relationship between extension and row planting in Ethiopia.
383 Surprisingly, we find no significant effects of farm size and land ownership on the adoption of
384 CSA despite their importance based in the literature (Khonje et al., 2018; Wainaina et al., 2016;
385 Bezu et al., 2014; Kamau et al., 2014).

386

387 *4.2 Impacts of CSA on farm and welfare outcomes*

388 Table 4 highlights the impact of CSA on yield, sales intensity, and own consumption per AEU
389 under actual and counterfactual conditions after controlling for selection bias. The results from the
390 second stage regression show that some of the time averages and selection correction terms are
391 significant in most of the outcome equations. Table A3 in the appendix presents the results of the
392 unconditional average effects (an indication of the effect of CSA on outcomes) of adoption on
393 yield, intensity of commercialization, and own consumption per AEU derived from the actual and

394 counterfactual distributions. On the average, adopters of **CSA** recorded higher maize yield and
 395 intensity of commercialization than non-adopters. Conversely, non-adopters of **CSA** realized
 396 higher own consumption per AEU than adopters. These results do not account for selection bias
 397 due to both observed and unobserved factors. However, the results in Table 4 accounts for
 398 selectivity bias.

399

400 Table 4: Impact of **CSA** on yield and food security

Outcome variables	Technology choice	Adoption status		Average treatment effect on treated
		Adopters	Non-adopters	
Maize yield (kg/ha)	IMP ₁ ROW ₀	927.14 (55.26)	804.74 (95.13)	122.40* (91.82)
	IMP ₀ ROW ₁	1098.16 (36.71)	827.66 (57.39)	270.50*** (66.39)
Sales intensity	IMP ₁ ROW ₀	1.62 (0.02)	1.54 (0.03)	0.09*** (0.03)
	IMP ₀ ROW ₁	1.68 (0.02)	1.55 (0.02)	0.13*** (0.02)
Own consumption per AEU	IMP ₁ ROW ₀	1.57 (0.04)	1.57 (0.02)	-0.00 (0.04)
	IMP ₀ ROW ₁	1.56 (0.03)	1.67 (0.03)	-0.11*** (0.03)

401 *Notes:* The reference category is non-adoption (IMP₀ROW₀); IMP₁ROW₀— adoption of only DTM maize varieties; IMP₀ROW₁—
 402 only row planting; AEU refers to adult equivalent unit. **The values in parentheses are standard errors.** The mean values of yield,
 403 intensity of commercialization, and own consumption for the non-adoption category are 1094.78 kg/ha, 0.68, and 0.58 respectively.
 404 *Source:* Authors computation based on IITA-IFPRI panel survey, 2018.

405

406 The results show that adoption of **CSA** impacts positively on maize yield. The adoption of row
 407 planting (IMP₀ROW₁) recorded the highest positive yield effect (271 kg/ha) followed by the
 408 adoption of DTM varieties (IMP₁ROW₀) which increases maize yield by 122 kg/ha. In eastern
 409 Zambia, Khonje et al. (2015) find a positive effect of improved maize varieties on yield. Alemu et
 410 al. (2014) observe that row planting increases yield by 14% in Ethiopia. Contrary to our findings,
 411 Vandercasteelen et al. (2018) did not find any significant effect of row planting on teff yield in
 412 Ethiopia.

413

414 With respect to the intensity of commercialization, the results show that on the average adopters
 415 of **CSA** are more likely sell a larger share of their maize. **The results indicate that both DTM seed**

416 and row planting have differential effects on the intensity of maize commercialization. For
417 example, while adopters of row planting (IMP_0ROW_1) recorded relatively higher positive intensity
418 of maize commercialization of 0.13, adopters of DTM varieties (IMP_1ROW_0) realized the lowest
419 intensity of maize commercialization (0.09). We expect higher maize yield to translate to higher
420 market participation assuming market conditions are favourable to smallholder farmers. Farm
421 households participate in output markets to generate income in order to meet household
422 expenditures. In addition, they participate in market to diversify their food choices by exchanging
423 own production with other food items not produced within the households. The results suggest that
424 by encouraging the use of CSA, there is the likelihood of increasing market participation that will
425 translate to higher income and increase food choices within farm households.

426

427 The results reveal that adoption of CSA reduces own consumption per AEU. Adoption of only
428 improved maize varieties have a negligible negative effect on own consumption per AEU while
429 adoption of row planting (IMP_0ROW_1) have a negative effect on own consumption per AEU.
430 These results are expected given that adoption of CSA increases household maize
431 commercialization intensity thus the quantity of own consumption would also be expected to
432 decline. It is possible that reduction in own consumption may be complemented with increase in
433 consumption of other food items not directly produced by the households. Household food
434 diversification may be driving the negative effect of CSA on own consumption. Our results
435 contradict Fentie and Beyene (2019) and Bezu et al. (2014) who find a positive effect of improved
436 maize adoption on own consumption per AEU in Malawi and Ethiopia, respectively.

437

438

439 4.3 Alternative specifications: IV-fixed effects

440 To check for robustness of our results, we use an alternative specification (IV fixed effects panel
 441 regression) that account for the endogeneity in the choice of **CSA**. The results of this estimation
 442 are reported in Table 5. The estimation is consistent with the previous findings where adoption of
 443 **CSA** impacts positively on maize yield and intensity of maize commercialization but impact
 444 negatively on own consumption per AEU. However, the magnitudes of the effects of adoption on
 445 maize yield and own consumption per AEU is consistently lower for the MESR-based estimates
 446 (Table 4) compared to the IV-fixed effects (Table 5). With the exception of adopters of only DTM
 447 varieties, the magnitudes of the MESR-based estimates is consistently higher for row planting
 448 relative to the IV-fixed effects estimates. Despite the differences in the scale of effect, our results
 449 show that adoption of **CSA** influences farm and welfare outcomes

450

451 Table 5: Robustness checks on welfare effects of adopting CSA

Choices of CSA	Instrumental Variable Fixed Effects		
	Maize yield	Sales intensity	Own consumption
IMP ₁ ROW ₀	403.34** (176.65)	0.19*** (0.03)	-0.73** (0.36)
IMP ₀ ROW ₁	342.14*** (3.05)	0.04*** (0.01)	-0.95* (0.57)

452 *Note:* Robust standard errors are in parentheses. The mean values of yield, intensity of commercialization, and own
 453 consumption for the non-adoption category are 1094.78 kg/ha, 0.68, and 0.58 respectively.

454

455

456 5. Conclusion

457 Most studies in SSA have focused on the adoption of single agricultural technologies on the
 458 welfare of smallholder farmers. Yet little is known about the impact of row planting on farm and
 459 welfare outcomes despite vigorous promotion of CSA practices by development organizations.
 460 This paper examines the adoption and farm and welfare impacts of **CSA** using a recent panel data
 461 from Ghana. We employ a multinomial endogenous switching regression model to correct for
 462 endogeneity and selection bias in the choice of **CSA**.

463

464 Our results suggest that adoption of DTM varieties is generally high over the period of study but
465 the adoption of row planting decreased for the same period. In promoting CSA among smallholder
466 farmers, key factors to consider include gender, years of formal education, distance to farm plots,
467 fertilizer use, inter-cropping, assets ownership, and access to extension services. Our results further
468 showed that adoption of CSA increases maize yields and intensity of maize commercialization but
469 decreases own consumption per AEU. In terms of heterogeneity effect, we find evidence of higher
470 effect of adoption of row planting on maize yield, commercialization intensity and own
471 consumption per AEU relative to the adoption of only DTM varieties. However, the study is
472 limited in identifying whether a decrease in own consumption increases consumption of food away
473 from home and non-food expenditures.

474

475 Our results provide valuable information about the choice of CSA that can benefit smallholder
476 farmers taking into consideration the resource constraints they face. However, these gains may be
477 consolidated when the gender inequality gap in terms of access to technology is addressed coupled
478 with increasing the visibility of agricultural technologies through extension agents. From policy
479 perspective, farmers must be encouraged to use row planting as a strategy to increase agricultural
480 performance and welfare outcomes. This can be achieved by using extension agents to create
481 awareness coupled with farmer trainings programs. Furthermore, adoption of CSA have the
482 tendency to increase household food diversification due to the decrease in own consumption per
483 AEU.

484 Although this study is informative, lack of data on other CSA and the short panel of the data-set
485 limits detail analysis of the variation in the use of CSA. We are unable to conduct a benefit cost

486 analysis that will inform policy-makers on which of the choices of CSA is more economically
487 rewarding and cost-effective. Second, the study will benefit much from using the area under each
488 of the practices as intensity measurement relative to count measurement. Third, establishing the
489 relationship between adoption of CSA and own consumption and food purchases to supplement
490 household nutrition requirement is key. These remain for the future.

491

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665 **Appendices**

666 Table A1: Test of the validity of the instrument (falsification test)

Panel A	Maize yield [†]		
	IMP ₀ ROW ₀ (1)	IMP ₁ ROW ₀ (2)	IMP ₀ ROW ₁ (3)
Extension contact farmer	-0.087 (0.173)	0.079 (0.095)	-0.052 (0.187)
Farmer contact extension	-0.196 (0.196)	0.055 (0.096)	0.104 (0.174)
Distance to extension (log)	-	-0.002 (0.002)	0.002 (0.001)
F-values	F(2, 101)=0.75	F(3, 339)=0.79	F(3, 70)=0.67
Panel B	Sales intensity [†]		
	IMP ₀ ROW ₀ (1)	IMP ₁ ROW ₀ (2)	IMP ₀ ROW ₁ (3)
Extension contact farmer	0.034 (0.034)	-0.021 (0.019)	-0.049 (0.042)
Farmer contact extension	0.006 (0.037)	0.022 (0.019)	-0.009 (0.039)
Distance to extension (log)	-0.001 (0.002)	-0.000 (0.00)	0.000 (0.000)
F-values	F(3, 113)=0.49	F(3, 340)=0.70	F(3, 70)=1.16
Panel C	Own consumption [†]		
	IMP ₀ ROW ₀ (1)	IMP ₁ ROW ₀ (2)	IMP ₀ ROW ₁ (3)
Extension contact farmer	0.072 (0.052)	0.014 (0.038)	0.111 (0.083)
Farmer contact extension	-	0.014 (0.038)	0.003 (0.078)
Distance to extension (log)	-	-	-0.001 (0.001)
F-values	F(1, 115)=1.93	F(2, 341)=0.18	F(3, 70)=1.25

667 Notes: IMP₀ROW₀ is the reference category. [†] indicate variables expressed in natural logarithm. Standard errors are
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Table A2: Descriptive statistics by survey year and adoption status

Variable	2013						2018					
	IMP ₀ ROW ₀		IMP ₁ ROW ₀		IMP ₀ ROW ₁		IMP ₀ ROW ₀		IMP ₁ ROW ₀		IMP ₀ ROW ₁	
	Mean	SD										
Yield	1144	1077	1200	983	1332	1028	961	552	1160	1690	1301	1169
Sales intensity	0.67	0.32	0.77	0.24	0.75	0.25	0.70	0.36	0.61	0.32	0.54	0.31
Own consumption	0.55	0.67	0.63	0.68	0.47	0.44	0.64	0.84	0.70	0.95	1.03	1.05
Age	45.2	13.6	44.4	11.8	44.6	11.9	48.0	12.0	50.8	10.9	47.5	11.5
Education (years)	4.7	4.9	5.4	4.8	6.2	5.0	3.1	4.9	4.2	5.4	4.8	5.9
Nativity	0.7	0.5	0.6	0.5	0.6	0.5	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.5	0.7	0.5
Household size	9.7	6.2	9.0	7.1	8.7	6.2	6.0	6.9	9.1	8.9	10.0	4.2
Intercropping	0.6	0.5	0.6	0.5	0.4	0.5	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.3	0.0	0.2
Plot distance	43.2	40.3	47.4	38.3	37.6	33.3	28.4	35.7	43.6	35.3	33.9	40.4
Owns land	3.3	2.0	3.3	1.7	3.5	1.8	1.7	1.8	3.1	1.4	3.0	1.6
Plot size	1.6	1.3	1.9	2.2	1.6	1.8	1.4	1.0	1.9	2.3	1.7	1.9
Land slope	0.4	0.5	0.4	0.5	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.5	0.3	0.4	0.4	0.5
Used fertilizer	0.2	0.4	0.3	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.4	0.5	0.4	0.5	0.8	0.4
Model farmer	0.3	0.4	0.2	0.4	0.2	0.4	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.3
Fertilizer use (years)	1.5	3.1	2.0	3.6	3.1	3.4	2.7	4.1	2.6	4.2	6.6	6.5
Owns bicycle	0.4	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.7	0.4	1.0	0.2	1.0	0.2
Owns motor	0.2	0.4	0.2	0.4	0.2	0.4	0.7	0.4	1.0	0.2	1.0	0.2
Owns sprayer	0.5	0.5	0.6	0.5	0.7	0.5	0.7	0.4	0.9	0.3	1.0	0.2
Distance to extension	19.5	68.8	8.0	8.2	10.3	12.0	5.1	7.6	8.9	13.7	7.0	6.2
Member of FBO	0.2	0.4	0.3	0.5	0.2	0.4	0.4	0.5	0.3	0.5	0.5	0.5
Contact extension	0.1	0.3	0.2	0.4	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.5	0.3	0.5	0.7	0.5
Extension contact	0.3	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.6	0.5	0.4	0.5	0.8	0.4

691 Notes: The reference category is non-adoption (IMP₀ROW₀). IMP₁ROW₀— only improved maize varieties;
692 IMP₀ROW₁—only row planting; SD refers to standard deviations. Source: Authors estimation based on IITA-IFPRI
693 panel survey, 2018.

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Table A3: Unconditional average effects of adoption of CSA on yield and food security

Outcome variables	Technology choice	Adoption status		Unconditional average effect
		Adopters	Non-adopters	
Maize yield (kg/ha)	IMP ₁ ROW ₀	1115.67 (31.67)	871.44 (29.62)	244.23*** (36.63)
	IMP ₀ ROW ₁	1109.63 (18.96)	871.44 (29.62)	238.19*** (31.63)
Sales intensity	IMP ₁ ROW ₀	1.68 (0.01)	1.58 (0.01)	0.10***(0.01)
	IMP ₀ ROW ₁	1.68 (0.01)	1.58 (0.01)	0.10*** (0.01)
Own consumption per AEU	IMP ₁ ROW ₀	1.68 (0.02)	1.62 (0.01)	0.06 (0.11)

	IMP ₀ ROW ₁	1.57 (0.03)	1.62 (0.01)	-0.05** (0.02)
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697 *Notes:* The reference category is non-adoption (IMP₀ROW₀); IMP₁ROW₀— only DTM varieties; IMP₀ROW₁— only row planting.
698 AEU refers to adult equivalent unit. The mean values of yield, intensity of commercialization, and own consumption for the non-
699 adoption category are 1094.78 kg/ha, 0.68, and 0.58 respectively. *Source:* Authors computation based on IITA-IFPRI panel survey,
700 2018.
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Author Statement

The authors declare that this manuscript is original and there is no conflict of interest